

MICROSTRUCTURE CHARACTERIZATION AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF C35/C45 STEELS USING MAGNETIC BARKHAUSEN NOISE ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT: *The aim of this work is to use Magnetic Barkhausen Noise (MBN) as a non-destructive evaluation technique for the microstructural analysis of C35 and C45 steels. In this sense, three different heat treatments were applied to these two steels to obtain different microstructures with different volume fractions of the constituents. Magnetic Brkhausen measurements have been performed using the MikroMach instrument. The results of this study demonstrate that not only are the Barkhausen noise measurements highly sensitive to the determination of carbon content and the state of internal stresses of two steels, but they also give a very precise idea of the constituents and the morphologies of the microstructures. Finally, this study establishes the relationship between the various microstructures and magnetic properties (H_c) and mechanical properties, particularly Vickers hardness (H_v), for each applied heat treatment.*

KEYWORDS: *Non-destructive characterization, Magnetic Barkhausen Noise (MBN), C35/C45 steels, Heat treatments, Microstructural characterization, Vickers hardness*

INTRODUCTION

Nondestructive testing and evaluation “NDT and E” of carbon content and mechanical properties of steels, in particular the hardness and internal stresses, would fulfill a strong industrial need. The steels with carbon ranging from 0.40% to 0.60% are mainly used in many industries such as machinery and construction, for making shafts, rail axles, gears, crankshafts, couplings, and forgings due to its high strength and hardness [1-6]. The microstructure of hypoeutectoid carbon steels shows ferrite and pearlite bands with different volume fraction of constituent [7,8]. However, the classic NDT&E techniques are unable to differentiate the information associated with the microstructures morphologies produced by different heat treatments. Therefore, Magnetic Barkhausen Noise “MBN” analysis discovered in 1919 [9], provides a precise, non-destructive method for evaluating ferromagnetic steels [10-13].

MBN originates from discontinuous magnetization changes in ferromagnetic material under the influence of a time-varying magnetic fields [14]. MBN is mainly produced by the changes of Bloch walls (BWs) arrangement and of the microstructure (dislocations, precipitates and residual stresses),

hardness [15,16] and discontinuous motion of domain walls (DWs) during magnetization under a continuously varying magnetic field. The discovery of this phenomenon, which experimentally proves the existence of magnetic domains in ferromagnetic materials [17,18], allows Barkhausen noise to be used in the evaluation of the morphology of the microstructure, the state of internal stresses, hardness, ... [19]. In ferromagnetic materials, two types of Bloch walls. The 180° Bloch walls possess greater mobility than the 90° walls, making their contribution to MBN more significant [13], the stepwise pull-out of the Bloch wall from the microstructure obstacle, changes the magnetization state locally. It is called a Barkhausen event [20-22]. In this work, two types of carbon steels (C35 and C45) were chosen to evaluate the sensitivity of the non-destructive MBN technique to differentiate the carbon content in steels, as well as the microstructures produced on the two steels by different heat treatments. For this, three different heat treatments were applied on C35 and C45 steels to develop various microstructure morphologies Barkhausen noise (MBN) analysis. This study investigated the relationship between MBN activity and microstructural characteristics of heat treated

steels, as well as the correlation between their magnetic and mechanical properties.

MATERIAL AND EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

Steels and heat treatments

To be able to study the sensitivity of Magnetic Barkhausen Noise (MBN) on the carbon content of steels and microstructure changes, we chose to work on C35 and C45 carbon steels, which are widely used in the manufacture of mechanical parts. These two steels have a slight difference in carbon content of around 0.1% and make it possible to obtain different microstructures and different proportions of the constituents of the microstructures through heat

treatments. Table 1 and Table 2 show the chemical composition and the principal mechanical properties of these steels.

Two different sample sizes were prepared for each steel type (C45 and C35) to perform various analyses: small specimens measuring 10 mm × 10 mm × 10 mm for microstructural analysis, and larger specimens measuring 70 mm × 70 mm × 10 mm for MBN measurements.

The initial microstructures of C35 and C45 steels are shown in Fig1. and it consists of ferrite and pearlite mixtures with different phase volume fractions.

Table 1. Chemical composition (in weight percent.%) of C35 and C45 steels.

Grade	C	Si	Mn	P	S	Cr	Mo	Ni	Cu	Co	Al	Nb	Ti	B	Fe
C35	0.39	0.187	0.721	0.006	0.0246	0.188	0.030	0.078	0.236	0.009	0.025	<0.004	0.0015	<0.0002	Balance
C45	0.50	0.134	0.727	0.0043	0.0219	0.180	0.041	0.159	0.204	0.0096	0.0149	<0.004	0.0036	<0.0002	Balance

Table 2. Mechanical properties of C35 and C45 steels.

Grade	Young modulus E	Stress Rp0.2%	The cyclic yield limit Rpc0.2%	The ultimate tensile strength Rm	Fracture elongation A
C35	205 Gpa	350 Mpa	280 MPa	580 Mpa	18%
C45	210 Gpa	560 Mpa	410 MPa	820 Mpa	15%

(a)

(b)

Fig. 1 Microstructure of steels samples in the initial state with ferrite and pearlite phases:(a) C35 steel and (b) C45 steel

To examine the microstructural evolution during different types of heating in C35 and C45 steels, a set of interrupted heating experiments was performed using a electric Muffle Furnace.

In order to obtain various microstructures and morphologies, we applied to C35 and C45 steels three different heat treatments, as shown in Fig. 2.

- The first treatment: Austenization at 850°C for 0.5 h, then cooling in the furnace at 600°C for 1.5 h, and finally cooling in the air until the ambient temperature.
- The second treatment (two-stage process). Full austenization at 850°C for 0.5 h, then controlled cooling in a furnace to 450°C for 0.5 h, followed by final air cooling in air until the ambient temperature
- The third treatment: employed direct intercritical annealing at 850°C for 0.5 hours with immediate water quenching to complete the process.

Optical and SEM characterization

Before the Metallography and Microstructures analysis, all specimens were progressively polished using Silicon Carbide (SiC) abrasive papers with sequentially increasing grit sizes (80 to 3000). This protocol ensured complete removal of surface oxides and deformation layers, producing a mirror-finish surfaces. To study the microstructure, some samples were etched for 10 seconds in Nital solution of (3 mL nitric acid+ 100mL ethanol).

Fig. 2 Schematic diagram of various heat treatment processes.

The microstructures examinations were performed using both optical microscope and scanning electron microscope (SEM). The volume fraction of ferrite, pearlite, bainite and martensite in the microstructures obtained by the three heat

treatments was calculated using image analysis with **ImageJ**® software. To increase precision, the analyzes were carried out on four pictures, and the average of these values is taken as the volume fraction for the sample.

Hardness tests

Microhardness measurements were carried out with Th-180 Hardness Testing System durometer. Five measurements have been performed on each sample at different area, and the average value was taken as the microhardness of this sample. All values are converted to Vickers Hardness (HV).

Micro-Magnetic testing systems

The measurements were carried out using MikroMaCh system (Micro-Magnetic Material Characterization) as shown in Fig. 3. The testing systems induce a cyclic magnetization to enable a non-destructive analysis of microstructural and mechanical properties related to the magnetization behavior of (ferromagnetic) materials measurement principles include MBN [23].

Fig. 3 Experimental Set-up for measurement of Barkhausen noise.

The Root Mean Square (RMS) signal corresponds to its envelope, is plotted as a function of the applied magnetic field, and characterized by two parameters: as the maximum amplitude of the noise (M_{max}) and the corresponding magnetic field (H_c) as shown in Fig. 4.

In the majority of measurements as the Barkhausen noise is symmetrical in relation to the null magnetic field, we get only the positive parts of the curve which we plotted.

Fig. 4 RMS signal of the Barkhausen noise curve with selected measured parameters. MBN: Barkhausen noise amplitude; H: exterior magnetic field.

Five measuring points, separated by 20 mm from each other, were defined for the MBN measurements. The instrumentation consists of an excitation loop that produces an alternating magnetic field in the sample and detected the signal response via a MikroMach magnetic sensor. To avoid errors during measurement, the position of the sensor was carefully placed perpendicular to the samples surface without lift-off between the sensor and the sample to get full contact with the surface. Finally, a sinusoidal magnetizing signal was produced with the voltage (Vm) at 50 A/cm at 40 Hz frequency (fm). The signal's filtering with a high-pass frequency was between (1–30 kHz).

The data was acquired, plotted and analyzed using the MikroMach software.

In this work, the MBN technique was used for the determination of the carbon content of C35 and C45 steels, the determination of the stress state of C35 and C45 steels in the initial state and after the application of heat treatments, as well as microstructural analysis of these states. Finally the comparison between the magnetic hardness obtained by the MBN signal with the Vickers hardness measured on the different samples.

RESULTS

Microstructures

Microstructures resulting from the three different heat treatments for C35 and C45 steels are shown in Fig5.

**Fig.5 Microstructure of C35 and C45 steels after three heat treatments(HT):
(a) C35 steel and (b) C45steel.**

Based on the microstructures obtained by the three heat treatments, we have the following remarks and findings:

- For the first Heat Treatment (HT-1) and for the two steels C35 and C45 (Fig. 5 HT-1a and HT-1b), we can easily see that the microstructure is dual-phase consisting of ferrite and pearlite with a volume fraction of pearlite very close to that of the initial state (Fig. 1a and 1b). However, it should be noted that, the proportion of pearlite is slightly higher in C45 steel (63.5 % for C45 steel compared to 47.5 % for C35 steel). This is not surprising, given that the carbon content of C45 steel is slightly higher than that of C35 steel. Indeed, it is well established that the proportion of pearlite increases with increasing carbon content in steels [24,25].
- In the Heat Treatment (HT-2), the pearlite observed in the C35 and C45 steels is transformed into bainite (Fig. 5 HT-2a and HT-2b). It is also observed that the distances between the bainite plates are finer in C45 steel

(286.5 nm) than in C35 steel (381.98 nm) Fig. 6. The volume fraction of the bainite is 47.2 % for C35 steel and 64.1 % for C45 steel. The bainite phase of the developed steel consists of coarse bainitic ferrite cells and austenite with precipitated carbides [26].

- Finally, for the third Heat Treatment (HT-3) the obtained microstructure consists of only martensite for the two steels C35 and C45 (Fig. 5 HT-3a and HT-3b). On these micrographs,

show that the martensite microstructure were is slightly fine in C45 steel compared to C35.

The volume fraction of the microstructure constitutes for the two steels C35 and C45 for the initial state, and after the three heat treatments calculated by ImageJ®, are grouped in Table 3.

The values of Vickers hardness (HV) of C35 and C45 steels, after the conversion, obtained directly from the different microstructures of the initial state, and after the three heat treatments are given in Table 4.

Fig6: Microstructures observed by SEM of bainite after the heat treatment (HT-2):

(a) C35 steel and (b) C45 steel.

Table. 3 The volume fraction of the microstructure constitutes of C35 and C45 steels in the initial state, and after the three heat treatments

Sample	Ferrite (Vol.%)	Pearlite (Vol.%)	Bainite (Vol.%)	Martensite (Vol.%)
C35 Steel				
Initial State (IS)	51.3 ± 0.2	48.7 ± 0.2	/	/
HT-1	52.5 ± 0.6	47.5 ± 0.6	/	/
HT-2	52.8 ± 0.1	/	47.2 ± 0.1	/
HT-3	/	/	/	100
C45 Steel				
Initial State (IS)	35.6 ± 0.4	64.4 ± 0.4	/	/
HT-1	36.5 ± 0.5	63.5 ± 0.5	/	/
HT-2	35.9 ± 0.2	/	64.1 ± 0.2	/
HT-3	/	/	/	100

Table. 4 The values of Vickers hardness (HV), of C35 and C45 steels for the initial state and after the three heat treatments.

Hardness (HV)				
Microstructure	Initial State (IS) Ferrite + Pearlite	HT-1 Ferrite + Pearlite	HT-2 Ferrite + Bainite	HT-3 Martensite
C35	160±2.2	155±2.1	305±4.6	529±8.5
C45	196±3.2	179±2.8	340±7.4	769±9.5

3.2. Magnetic Barkhausen noise signals measurement

Fig. 7 shows the RMS voltage as a function of the magnetic excitation field strength for the initial and heat-treated microstructures of C35 and C45 steels.

Based on the obtained results, we can make the following comments:

- The MBN signals obtained on C35 and C45 steels appear to be almost identical, regardless of the initial state or the applied heat treatment on these steels. However, it should be noted that the highest MBN signal amplitude M_{max} values of C35 steel are slightly higher than those of C45 steel in the dual-phase (ferrite + pearlite) and (bainitic ferrite) microstructures. The MBN signals demonstrate that barkhausen noise activity is sensitive to variations in the phase content of the microstructure.
- The comparison between the BNA signals of C35 and C45 steels in the initial state of microstructure (Ferrite + Pearlite) indicates that the M_{max} value of C35 steel is higher than that of C45 steel (0.772 mV against 0.88mV). The result can be interpreted by the processes of domain wall nucleation and wall propagation, which are affected by defects such as precipitates, grain boundaries and dislocations. MBN is proportional to the domain nucleation rate [27], The magnetostatic energy is gradually accumulated when carbide size increases with carbon. On the other hand, the magnetic hardness value of C45 steel is higher than that of C35 steel and varies between 1 and 3 A.cm⁻¹. This proves the high sensitivity of the MBN signal in differentiating the carbon content in carbon steels.
- The magnetic hardness of C35 and C45 steels after the first heat treatment (HT-1) are slightly lower than those in the initial state. This change is surely due to the effect of annealing which made it possible to homogenize and reduce or eliminate the residual stresses in the C35 and C45 steels, the difference varies between (4 and 7 A.cm⁻¹) for C35 and (3 and 6 A.cm⁻¹) for C45 steel. To understand this point, it should be recalled that internal stresses induced by the inhomogeneity of plastic deformation. This inhomogeneity of plastic deformation, from grain to grain, is the first source of residual internal stresses [28-30]. However, its influence of residual stresses and mobility of domain walls on MBN signals.

- In the second heat treatment (HT-2), we can see that the M_{max} of the MBN signals decreases whenever the microstructures changes from “ferrite + pearlite” to “ferrite + bainite” microstructures, and the magnetic hardness H_c increases. The shift of the Barkhausen noise peak toward lower magnetic field values reflects the strong influence of the material’s metallurgical condition on its magnetic properties. In addition, the MBN responses of C35 and C45 steels following the second heat treatment (HT-2) indicate that the C35 steel exhibits a lower M_{max} value compared to C45 steel. This indicates that the MBN signal is very sensitive to the volume fraction of microstructure constituents in steels.
- The microstructures obtained by the third heat treatment (HT-3) are the martensite needles, which cause low BN activity, and MBN peak is at lower magnetic fields due to small domain wall for two steels. But when compared C35 by C45 steels show that the martensite microstructure were is slightly fine in C 45. Thus, MBN activity gets higher in C35 steel, and the MBN peak is at low magnetic fields. The results show that the MBN signal are sensitive to tempering induced changes, and grain size differences.
- For each heat treatment, the MBN parameters M_{max} and H_c appear to follow a similar trend in both C35 and C45 steels, we see that the M_{max} decreases whenever the microstructures is change : ferrite pearlite(HT-1), ferrite pearlite at initial state, bainitic ferrite (HT-2) and martensitic microstructures (HT-3), and the H_c increases as well. The results show that the MBN signal can be affected by different heat treatments.

Globally, M_{max} is strongly dependent on the number of pinning obstacles met by Bloch walls. H_c is preferentially linked to the nature of obstacles [16]. As the influence of obstacles on the Bloch walls (BWs) decreases, the Barkhausen noise peak shifts to lower magnetic field values, due to the direct relationship between the material’s metallurgical state and its magnetic structure as shown in Fig. 6. However, this parameter is entirely dependent on configuration conditions, and calibration is required to determine all phase morphologies.

We also calculate the average (M_{max}) and (H_c) values, for each case. The values for each case are shown in Fig. 7, and are shown in Table 5.

Fig. 7 RMS of MBN signals for C35 and C45 steels at different microstructures.

Table .5 Average for Mmax and Hc of C35 and C45 steels at different microstructures.

Microstructure	HT-1 Ferrite + Pearlite	Initial State Ferrite + Pearlite	HT-2 Ferrite + Bainite	HT-3 Martensite
C35 Steel				
Hc(A/cm)	0.733 ± 0.01	6.881 ± 0.87	12.902 ± 1.20	30.291 ± 1.02
Mmax (mV)	0.827 ± 0.02	0.772 ± 0.01	0.622 ± 0.03	0.118 ± 0.03
C45 steel				
Hc(A/cm)	2.562 ± 0.42	8.155 ± 0.95	13.153 ± 1.32	34.208 ± 0.91
Mmax (mV)	0.940 ± 0.02	0.880 ± 0.01	0.790 ± 0.02	0.064 ± 0.00

3.3. Analysis of Results

The correlation graph illustrating the relationship between MBN parameters (M_{max} and H_c) and Vickers hardness is presented in Fig.8. based on the obtained results , it is observed that the variations in MBN emissions (M_{max}) across the different heat treated sampls decrease with increasing Vickers hardness, this suggests a relationship between domain wall movement , residual stresses, and the amount of phases in the microstructure. The average domain wall jump size in ferritic–pearlitic microstructure is larger compared to that observed in ferritic-pearlitic in initial state with internal stress, as well as in bainitic and martensitic structures. As shown in Fig.8, the MBN values exhibit an inverse correlation with Vickers hardness. This trend suggests that as the material becomes harder due to changes in microstructure such as the formation of bainite or martensite, or the presence of internal stresses, the mobility of magnetic domain walls is increasingly

restricted. Consequently, the Barkhausen noise signal amplitude decreases. This relationship highlights the sensitivity of MBN activity to the

mechanical and microstructural properties of C35 and C45 steels.

Fig 8. Evolution of MBN parameters (Mmax and Hc) as a function of Mechanical Hardness « HV » in the initial state (IS) and heat-treated conditions (HT-1, HT-2 et HT-3) : (a) C35 steel and (b) C45 Steel.

4. COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF RESPONSES TO BARKHAUSEN MAGNETIC NOISE: EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND CRITICAL LITERATURE REVIEW

According to Samimi et al. [34], Barkhausen noise (BN) can be used to assess the carbon content in carbon steels over a wide range of 0.18% to 0.95% carbon, in both annealed and quenched states. Our results on C35 and C45 steels in the annealed state confirm this conclusion, showing a clear correlation between BN activity and carbon content. On the other hand, the work of Ng et al. [32] demonstrated the effectiveness of the RMS of Barkhausen emission (BE) signals in evaluating the carbon content of carbon steels, with an applicable range of 0.1% to 0.97% carbon. While our findings on C35 and C45 steels (0.39% and 0.50% carbon in the annealed state) support this approach, they also

reveal a notable correlation between MBN parameters (M_{max} and H_c) and carbon content.

Although our study focused specifically on C35 and C45 steels (containing 0.39% and 0.50% carbon, respectively), research by other authors[32–34] on various types of steel grades (low-alloy steels, DP steels, TRIP steels, HSLA steels, etc.) has also demonstrated the effectiveness of BN in evaluating carbon content in these steel grades.

According to Saquet et al. [35], MBN parameters are particularly effective in characterizing different phases in carbon steels (ferrite, pearlite, martensite). They found that ferrite exhibits very intense BN activity, pearlite shows intermediate activity, and martensite exhibits weak activity. Similarly, in our results for C35 and C45 steels, the maximum BN activity was observed in the pearlitic structure, intermediate activity in the bainitic structure, and the lowest activity in the martensitic structure.

Other studies [16,29,31–35] involving microstructural characterization of heat-treated steels have confirmed that Barkhausen noise is a versatile and reliable tool for such investigations. Indeed, Gür [29] observed a 70–75% reduction in BN activity in martensitic structures compared to pearlitic ones, which aligns with our findings on C35 and C45 steels. The work of Hug-Amalric et al. [16,31] quantified the effect of phases in DP and TRIP steels and found that BN is inversely proportional to the martensite fraction in DP steels, while an increase in bainite content in TRIP steels enhances BN activity. The same trend was observed in the bainitic structures of our C35 and C45 steels. These findings further validate the sensitivity of the Barkhausen noise technique in characterizing steel microstructures specifically the presence and proportion of ferrite, pearlite, bainite, and martensite.

The present work systematically examines Barkhausen noise (BN) activity in C35 and C45 steels. The data collected, while confirming general trends reported in the literature, provide a more comprehensive characterization of microstructural influences.

Table 6 summarizes various studies on Barkhausen noise responses in different steel grades, including the C35 and C45 steels used in this study.

Table .6 Contrasting MBN Characteristics in C35/C45 Steels with Prior Studies.

Inspected property	Material	C%	Heat Treatment	Microstructure	Hardness (HV)	Used Parameters of BN Signal	BN Trend vs. Key Parameter	Ref
Ferrite % quantification	DP Steels*	0.09-0.180.34	Intercritical Annealing	F+ M	220-280~350	RMS amplitude, H _c ,	Decreases with M increase, H _c rises with M	[31]

			/Quenched					
Ferrite % quantification	DP Steels*	0.09-0.18	Intercritical Annealing + Quenched	F + M/B	220-280	RMS amplitude, Hc	Amplitude rises with F, Hc drops with F	[16]
Phase signatures	DP Steels*	0.48	Intercritical Annealing	F + M	~350	Two-peak signal	Decreases with M, Hc rises with M	
Bainite % quantification	TRIP Steels	0.21	Austempering	F + B + A	N/A	BNA, Hc	BNA rises with B	
Tempering evaluation	AISI/SAE 4140	0.40	Quenched + Tempered	M → TM	300-600	RMS, Peak Field	Increases with tempering, Peak Field drops	[33]
Carbon content /stress evaluation	Plain Carbon Steels	0.18-0.95	Annealed/Stressed	F + P	N/A	BN Energy, Envelope, Hc	Energy peaks at 0.65% C then drops, Hc rises with carbon, Energy rises with stress	[34]
Phase identification	Plain Carbon Steels	0.1-0.8	Annealed/Quenched	F, P, M	N/A	MBN/ABN	Ferrite: High BN, Pearlite: Moderate, Martensite: Low	[35]
Microstructure characterization and Hardness correlation	AISI 1040	0.40	Quenched, Air-cooled, Furnace-cooled - Varied cooling rates	M, F + P	180-660	MBN signal, Peak height, Magnetic excitation field	decreases with increasing HV (M > fine P > coarse P); Peak shifts to lower fields for softer phases	[29]
Carbon content, phase quantification and Hardness correlation	C35/C45 Steels	0.39/0.50	Intercritical Annealing, Quenching	F + P, F + B, M	C35 : 160-529 C45 : 196-769	RMS (Mmax, Hc)	BN decreases with B/M; Hc increases with C and residual stresses. Inverse correlation with Hv.	This work

5. CONCLUSION

The present experimental work has led to the following conclusions:

A new methodology of non-destructive testing consisting of carbon content analysis, hardness evaluation and microstructure characterization based on the Barkhausen noise measurements.

The magnetic excitation field H_c , increases proportionally to the rate of the carbon equivalent content in the steels, varies between 1 and 3 A.cm⁻¹. The Barkhausen noise activity of C45 is lower than that of C35. Specifically, the maximum amplitude of the Barkhausen signal (M_{max}) decreases when the rate of carbon equivalent in the steels increases.

This study demonstrates that Barkhausen noise (MBN) is a sensitive tool for characterizing

microstructural phases in steels. The results reveal a clear hierarchy in MBN activity: the ferritic-pearlitic microstructure shows the most intense signal, followed by an intermediate response for bainite, while martensite exhibits the weakest MBN activity. More specifically, as the magnetic excitation field H_c increases, the MBN signal from martensite reaches its minimum level (lowest M_{max}), highlighting its enhanced sensitivity to magnetic conditions.

Through quantitative analysis of MBN parameters, residual stress, hardness testing and metallographic analysis, this study we have establishes a clear relationship between coercive field (H_c), Vickers hardness (HV), and microstructural evolution in heat-treated C35 and C45 steels

6. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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8. NOTATION

NDT and E = Nondestructive testing and evaluation;

MBN = Magnetic Barkhausen Noise

IAT = Inter-critical annealing temperature

HT = Heat Treatment

M_{\max} = Maximum amplitude (mV)

f = Frequency (kHz).

H_c = Magnetic hardness(A/cm)

HV = Mechanical hardness

V = voltage A/cm

N/A =Not Applicable

P = Pearlite

B = Bainite

M = Martensite

TM = Tempered martensite

A = Austenite

C = Cementite

RS = Rising slope

HMW = Half-max-width

DP = Dual phase